

Gain Scheduling Control System for a Reconfigurable Underwater Vehicle for Inspection, Free-Floating Intervention and Survey Tasks

1st Mirco Vangi¹
mirco.vangi@unifi.it

2nd Edoardo Topini¹
edoardo.topini@unifi.it

3rd Gherardo Liverani¹
gherardo.liverani@unifi.it

4th Alessandro Bucci¹
alessandro.bucci@unifi.it

5th Alberto Topini¹
alberto.topini@unifi.it

6th Alessandro Ridolfi¹
alessandro.ridolfi@unifi.it

7th Benedetto Allotta¹
benedetto.allotta@unifi.it

¹Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Florence

Abstract—Underwater environments may result in a challenging scenario in which several complex goals have to be performed. These tasks are usually carried out by using remote-controlled or autonomous robots, which largely reduce the cost and increase the safety of these operations. As a consequence, the interest in underwater robots is rapidly increased in the past few decades. More in detail, the last trends in marine robotics regard underwater vehicles with the ability to change their current configuration depending on the task to be accomplished. Concerning this particular topic, the Department of Industrial Engineering at the University of Florence (DIEF) has developed the innovative RUVIFIST vehicle (Reconfigurable Underwater Vehicle for Inspection, Free-floating Intervention and Survey Tasks), that can switch from two extreme configurations. In the context of this work, the authors present the methodologies used in adapting and extending the standard control system, employed to handle a time-varying system as a reconfigurable robot.

Index Terms—Underwater Robotics, Autonomous Underwater Reconfigurable Vehicles, Marine Robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

During the past few decades, the interest in underwater robotics has significantly increased. Underwater environments are very challenging scenarios for humans and the possibility of replacing human operators with robots in such situations has caught the interest of companies, researchers and the military. While early submarine robots prototype were principally tasked with inspecting an area of interest, nowadays they are often required to perform intervention operations even in fully or partially unknown environments. For instance, the Oil&Gas industry has a growing demand for new and innovative solutions for the inspection, maintenance, and repair of seabed installations. These tasks are currently carried out by Remotely Underwater Vehicles (ROVs) deployed from a large surface vessel. ROVs are generally teleoperated vehicles connected by a cable to a control station where a trained operator guides the vehicle. Due to the requirements of a

surface vessel, these operations are very expensive and, the requested cable connection introduces a limit on the maximum depth that a vehicle can reach. In order to reduce the costs of the inspection task and deal with several logistic constraints, the interest in Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) is rapidly increased in the last decades. More specifically, AUVs are completely autonomous vehicles equipped with battery packs and high-accurate navigation systems. AUVs are currently exploited for long-distance monitoring and inspection, as they present an accurate navigation model, while ROVs are used to perform more complex operations, as they present high manoeuvrability on all the Degrees Of Freedom (DOFs). As a result, the development of vehicles that can incorporate both the AUV inspection and ROV intervention functionalities can be considered a challenging task in the underwater industry as well as the scientific community. As a feasible solution for this goal, Autonomous Underwater Reconfigurable Vehicles (AURVs) can select the most appropriate configuration to dive with the optimal fluid dynamic efficiency and achieve the minimum power consumption for long-distance navigation (namely, in AUV modality); furthermore, the robot may be provided with a larger number of degrees of freedom for complex manipulation operations or to perform autonomous docking in a subsea station (namely, in ROV modality). Therefore, AURVs do arise as a promising tool for incorporating several reconfigurable modules and autonomously accomplishing inspection, surveys, and intervention tasks. One of the main problems related to AURV is the control system. By changing its configuration, the system model also changes, making it a very complex system to control. PID controller and Gain Scheduling techniques are two topics that are treated extensively and often even side by side in the scientific literature. The gain-schedule of PID control means that different sets of PID parameters are scheduled to pair up with different angles, enabling the

controller to function well in various situations [1]. An effective approach to solving the problem of the robust nonlinear control system design is the application of the Gain Scheduling (GS) with linear controllers, and PID is the simpler linear controller that can be implemented [2]. Shao *et al.* proposed a robust Gain-Scheduled PID (GS-PID) control applied on a Morphing Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (MUAV) [3]. In their work, the authors implemented a PID controller with the gains calculated from a Linear Parameter-Varying (LPV) model of the system, obtained by linearization in different operating points. The final controller is able to maintain a stable flight and track the pitch angle command during a complete opening and closing of the wings. Luna *et al.* applied GS-PID to a quad-rotor aerial drone equipped with a 2-DOF robotic arm [4]. In this case, the vehicle itself doesn't change its shape but the manipulation operations performed by the robotic arm change the dynamics of the vehicle making the overall system a time-varying system. In particular, they use the two angles that describe the robotic arm status to switch between the different PID gains. Differently from the previous work, the optimal value of the PID was obtained via experimental tests. GS-PID results to be a well-studied and widely used control strategy, as can be seen by the state-of-the-art review, however, its application on AURVs appears to be a field that has to be investigated more. In this work, we want to show the applicability of this control strategy also for a particular class of robots, the AURVs, by deploying a GS-PID controller on RUVIFIST.

In this paper, we are going to present the control system realized for RUVIFIST, explaining the solution proposed to deal with the time-varying dynamical model of the system.

II. THE RUVIFIST VEHICLE

The RUVIFIST (**R**econfigurable **U**nderwater **V**ehicle for **I**nspection, **F**ree-floating **I**ntervention, and **S**urvey **T**asks) vehicle is an innovative AURV developed at the Mechatronics and Dynamic Modeling Laboratory (MDM Lab) of the Department of Industrial Engineering of the University of Florence (DIEF). RUVIFIST is an AURV capable of efficiently reconfiguring its shape according to the task at hand, spanning from a “survey” (Figure 1a) slender configuration to a “hovering” stocky layout (Figure 1b).

Fig. 1: Render of the RUVIFIST vehicle in his survey (a) and hovering (b) configuration.

This vehicle features the capability to actively switch between a “hovering/opened” configuration, with an isotropic

behaviour proper to face intervention operations, and a “survey/closed” one, with an elongated body that minimizes the hydrodynamic damping force in the longitudinal direction and, as a consequence, reduces the power consumption for long mission tasks. More in detail, the survey configuration (Figure 1a) presents four thrusters along the surge direction and four in the heave direction. As a result, the sway motion is not permitted, leading to losing a Degree Of Mobility (DOM). On the other hand, the vehicle’s damping coefficient is minimal in this configuration, and the actuator layout system presents its best behaviour in the longitudinal motion, an ideal situation for survey tasks.

Turning to the hovering configuration properties (Figure 1b), the orientation of the horizontal plane thrusters is around 55° to the surge direction, leading to an approximately isotropic vehicle behaviour. With this distribution of the thrust forces, the vehicle also acquires the possibility to perform the movement in the sway direction, acquiring 6 DOFs and the possibility to perform hovering and further complex tasks.

As far as the reconfigurable system is concerned, the RUVIFIST AURV presents six different joints equipped with an absolute magnetic encoder, two of which are actuated with a bipolar stepper motor.

To correctly accomplish autonomous navigation missions the vehicle is equipped with a single-axis high-precision Fiber Optic Gyroscope (FOG) to estimate the vehicle’s heading, a Teledyne Wayfinder Doppler Velocity Log (DVL), to measure the linear velocity, and an Xsens MTi-300 Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), to monitor the roll and pitch angles. A more detailed description of the vehicle can be found in [5].

III. CONTROL SYSTEM

The most dynamic control algorithm widely used is a multivariable SISO (Single Input - Single Output) PID for each one of different DOF [6]. Referring to the application for reconfigurable vehicles, it is straightforward to observe that different vehicle configurations might lead to different dynamic behaviors. As a result, the gain scheduling methodology has been adopted in the context of this work for controlling nonlinear systems with dynamics changing from one operating condition to another. Therefore, the different controller gains must be tuned for each configuration of the robot or discretize the domain of the possible configuration in a finite subset with a linear interpolation among the several gains. More in particular, let be $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ a generic vehicle motion DOF, the robot controller is based on the following control law:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\tau}_c(\mathbf{q}) = & K_d(\mathbf{q})(\dot{\mathbf{x}}_d - \dot{\mathbf{x}}) + K_p(\mathbf{q})(\mathbf{x}_d - \mathbf{x}) + \\ & + K_i(\mathbf{q}) \int (\mathbf{x}_d - \mathbf{x}) dt \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where K_p , K_d , K_i are respectively the proportional, derivative and integral gain matrices which change depending on the vehicle configuration, and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_c(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the command force vector. Finally, it is worth noting that any model-based control has been adopted in the context of this work. Nevertheless, several model-based controllers will be tested in

the near future, spanning from feed-forward methods to more challenging controls.

Standard PID controllers are designed to work with Linear Time-Invariant (LTI) systems and are unable to handle Time-Varying Systems efficiently. GS-PID is a versatile technique which can be used for situations in which the parameters or the operating conditions of the process can change largely and rapidly [7]. A gain scheduling control system design takes the following steps [2]: linearization of the plant's model in the several equilibrium operating points, then tuning a local PID that meets the required performances and lastly implement the scheduling mechanism, thus establishing a scheduling variable $q(t)$ and a rule for changing the gains of the controller.

It is important to note that the scheduling variable may even not coincide with the system output, as long as it can be measured. In particular, we choose as scheduling variable the angle of the actuated joints, since it represents a parameter of the system that changes during the reconfiguration of the vehicle and that the encoders measure each different time step. As a consequence, the scheduling variable q has been employed to change the value of the controller gains which will therefore also depend, indirectly, on the time: $K_p(q)$, $K_i(q)$, $K_d(q)$. Furthermore, since the two actuated joints have almost the same angular position, the scheduling variable can be represented as a monodimensional time-varying value θ .

IV. RESULTS

To test the proposed control strategy several preliminary tests were performed during an experimental campaign in Roffia Lake, Pisa, Italy (see Figure 2). The first part of the trials was dedicated to evaluating the parameters of the proposed GS-PID controller. In particular, GS methodologies involve establishing the optimal controller in different configurations. In the context of our work, we have identified three different equilibrium points: the survey configuration ($\theta = 180^\circ$), the hovering configuration ($\theta = 110^\circ$) and an intermediate angular position ($\theta = 140^\circ$). Firstly, we heuristically evaluated the optimal values of K_p , K_i and K_d for each of these configurations. Subsequently, the interpolating function for each PID gain has been calculated and implemented within the vehicle control system.

In particular, the interpolating function results to be a cubic function so the variation of the controller gains does not exhibit discontinuities, which could lead to aggressive control actions and, possibly, instability.

A well-known problem correlated to PID control is the integrator windup. The problem occurs when the control requested action exceeds the maximum contribution that actuators can provide, making the error constant, and making the integral term larger and larger. To deal with this problem a clamping method was implemented in the PID class to limit the control action to a value equal to the max torques that the thrusters can provide in the actual configuration.

Once the identification phase was completed, a basic mission has been requested to be performed by the RUVIFIST AURV. More specifically, the vehicle was required to hold a

Fig. 2: The RUVIFIST vehicle in Roffia Lake during an experimental campaign.

fixed orientation during a complete morphing from the survey to the hovering configuration and viceversa. The complete mission was composed of several hierarchical stages: firstly, the vehicle reached and held the required pose for 30 seconds, subsequently, the vehicle switched its configuration from the survey to hovering, holding its pose for additional 30 seconds. Finally, the RUVIFIST AURV returns in the survey configuration while keeping the desired orientation. As previously explained, this mission was specifically performed to test the robustness of the designed time-varying control system during a complete robot transformation, and the results are reported in Figure 3.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented the control system implemented for the RUVIFIST vehicle, an innovative AURV developed by the Department of Industrial Engineering of the University of Florence.

Referring to this work, the control strategy have been specifically adapted and extended in the case of a reconfigurable vehicle.

The dynamic behaviour of the vehicle resulted in a non-linear time-varying system, so standard PID controllers cannot be used. As a result, a GS-PID methodology was accurately designed for this application, firstly estimating the optimal parameters for a fixed number of robot configurations, and then finding an interpolate function which provides the optimal value of the PID gains for each different value of the scheduling variable.

The gain scheduling controller was successfully tested at Roffia Lake, Pisa, Italy in 2023, testing the feasibility of the developed methodologies.

As future trends, the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms has arisen as innovative solutions for Automatic Target Recognition (ATR) [8] or dynamic modelling tasks [9], and will be faced in the near future. Driven by these considerations, the RUVIFIST vehicle will be provided with a perception payload composed of standard imaging devices, such as cameras and Forward-Looking Sonars.

Fig. 3: Results of the GS-PID control system for the roll, pitch, and yaw DOFs depending on the scheduling variable θ .

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Ye, "Moving least-squares based gain-schedule pid control for trajectory tracking of a robot," in *2021 International Conference on Communications, Information System and Computer Engineering (CISCE)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 251–255.
- [2] O. Nadsadna, "Design of robust gain scheduled control system," in *2015 IEEE International Conference Actual Problems of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles Developments (APUAVD)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 231–234.
- [3] P. Shao, Z. Zhou, S. Ma, and L. Bin, "Structural robust gain-scheduled pid control and application on a morphing wing uav," in *2017 36th Chinese Control Conference (CCC)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 3236–3241.
- [4] A. L. Luna, I. C. Vega, and J. M. Carranza, "Gain-scheduling and pid control for an autonomous aerial vehicle with a robotic arm," in *2018 IEEE 2nd Colombian conference on robotics and automation (CCRA)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–6.
- [5] E. Topini, G. Liverani, J. Gelli, C. Fredducci, A. Topini, A. Ridolfi, and B. Allotta, "Development and control of an autonomous reconfigurable underwater vehicle," in *OCEANS 2022, Hampton Roads, 2022*, pp. 1–6.
- [6] T. I. Fossen, *Guidance and Control of Ocean Vehicles*. Wiley, 1994.
- [7] W. J. Rugh and J. S. Shamma, "Research on gain scheduling," *Automatica*, vol. 36, no. 10, pp. 1401–1425, 2000.
- [8] L. Zacchini, M. Franchi, V. Manzari, M. Pagliai, N. Secciani, A. Topini, M. Stifani, and A. Ridolfi, "Forward-looking sonar CNN-based automatic target recognition: an experimental campaign with feelhippo auv," in *2020*

IEEE/OES Autonomous Underwater Vehicles Symposium (AUV). IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.

- [9] E. Topini, A. Topini, M. Franchi, A. Bucci, N. Secciani, A. Ridolfi, and B. Allotta, "LSTM-based dead reckoning navigation for autonomous underwater vehicles," in *Global Oceans 2020: Singapore – U.S. Gulf Coast, 2020*, pp. 1–7.